

Tricyclohexyl Tin Halides and Pseudohalides : Structural and Biocidal Activity

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A number of tricyclohexyltin compounds Cy_3SnX where $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NCS^- , NCO^- , NC^- , N_3^- , NCS_2^- or CH_3COO^- were obtained from metathetical or neutralization reactions and in case of $X=NCO$ and NCS by fusion of the tin oxide with urea and thiourea respectively. The nature of bonding in the pseudohalides has been discussed and some probable structures proposed. The antimicrobial activity against a number of pathogenic species have been tested and reported.

CYCLOHEXYLTIN compounds have recently been shown to possess some very interesting properties which place them in a special class. The biocidal activity of tricyclohexyltin compounds was initially reported in the patents¹⁻³ and the compounds are presently being manufactured commercially. One such compound is the tricyclohexyltinhydroxide $(C_6H_{11})_3SnOH$, trade name 'Plictran'⁴. Some unusual structural features associated with the steric hindrance offered by the cyclohexyl groups are also drawing considerable attention. Thus, the bonding in the tricyclohexyltin acetate and haloacetate permits a unidentate carboxylate linkage giving monomeric products^{5,6}, whereas all other known triorganotin acetates possess five coordinate tin with a polymeric structure⁷. Furthermore, the absence of amino group coordination to tin in the zwitterionic amino acids of triorganotin compounds⁸ and Mössbauer spectral data show that unlike similar compound the simple point charge model does not account for the quadrupole splitting of the cyclohexyltin derivatives⁶⁻⁹.

In continuation to our studies on various aspects of organotin and lead pseudohalides^{10,11}, we now report some synthetic and structural studies of tricyclohexyltin compounds, Cy_3SnX , where $Cy=Cyclo-C_6H_{11}$ and $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NCS^- , NCO^- , N_3^- , NC^- , NCS_2^- , CH_3COO^- , and the bis sulfide $(Cy_3Sn)_2S$ along with a comparative study of their biocidal activity against five species of bacteria and six species of fungi.

Materials and Method :

Tricyclohexyltin hydroxide : A Grignard solution was prepared from magnesium (35 g; 1.43 mole) and cyclohexyl bromide (200 g; 1.226 mole) in anhydrous ether, in a nitrogen atmosphere. The unreacted magnesium was removed by filtering through glass wool under nitrogen pressure. To the Grignard solution thus obtained, tin tetrachloride (70 g; 0.26 mole) in dry ether (150 ml)

was added dropwise during half an hour. The reaction mixture was stirred for further period of 1 hr followed by addition of benzene and refluxing for 6 hr. This gave Cy_3Sn on acid hydrolysis. The reaction of Cy_3Sn with bromine in CCl_4 gave excellent yield of tricyclohexyltin bromide (above 60%), m. p. 76° (lit.^{1,2} 77°). The ethanol solution of the bromide on further treatment with aqueous KOH gave Cy_3SnOH . Recrystallized from alcohol; m. p. $216-18^\circ$ (lit.^{1,2} $220-22^\circ$).

Cy_3SnX ($X=Cl$ and I) : The halides, chloride and iodide, were obtained in yields around 75-80% by the treatment of Cy_3SnOH with the corresponding hydrohalic acid in hot ethanol. The products obtained on concentration were washed twice with cold ethanol to remove the excess of acid and finally recrystallized from petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$). Cy_3SnCl , m.p. 128° (lit.^{1,2} $129-30^\circ$), Cy_3SnI ; m.p. 65° (lit.^{1,2} 65°).

$Cy_3SnOOCCH_3$: The acetate was prepared by the metathetical reaction between silver acetate and tricyclohexyltin iodide in refluxing benzene or sodium acetate and tricyclohexyltin chloride in absolute ethanol, as needle like crystals (yield 75%). The product was confirmed by mixed m.p. with a sample prepared by literature^{1,2} method viz heating tricyclohexyltin hydroxide with glacial acetic acid in ethanol.

Cy_3SnNCS_2 : Tricyclohexyltin selenocyanate was prepared by metathetical reaction. Thus, Cy_3SnCl (5 g; 0.012 mole) in 50 ml of chloroform and $KSeCN$ (2.16 g; 0.015 mole) in 25 ml of chloroform were mixed and stirred at room temperature for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated and the solid so obtained was recrystallized twice from petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$); yield 60%; m.p. $160-62^\circ$. Analysis; Found: C, 48.18; H, 6.99; N, 2.89; Sn, 24.99. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{36}N_2SnSe$; C, 48.23; H, 7.03; N, 2.96; Sn, 25.08%.

Cy_3SnN_3 : A solution of Cy_3SnCl (4 g; 0.009 mole) in 50 ml ether was mechanically stirred with concentrated aqueous solution of sodium azide in 20 ml of water at room temperature for 2 hr. The ether layer was washed twice with water to remove the excess of sodium azide, the solid obtained after removal of the ether was dried and recrystallized from petroleum ether; m.p. 104° (lit.¹⁴ 104°); yield 70%.

Cy_3SnNC : Silver cyanide (2.46 g; 0.018 mole) and tricyclohexyltin iodide (3 g; 0.006 mole) were refluxed for 2 hr in chloroform and stirred at room temperature for overnight. Filtration was followed by washing the residue with chloroform. The filtrate was evaporated to give 68% tricyclohexyltin cyanide recrystallized from chloroform/benzene mixture; m.p. 280° . Analysis; Found: C, 57.82; H, 8.38; N, 3.50; Sn, 30.08. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{36}NSn$; C, 57.89; H, 8.43; N, 3.55; Sn, 30.11%.

Cy_3SnNCO : It was prepared by the metathetical reaction of silver cyanate with tricyclohexyltin iodide in chloroform at room temperature. The precipitated silver iodide was filtered off and the filtrate on concentration yielded tricyclohexyltin isocyanate which was recrystallized from petroleum ether/chloroform mixture; m.p. 101° .

Tricyclohexyltin isocyanate was also prepared by fusion of Cy_3SnOH and urea in nitrogen atmosphere. Thus, Cy_3SnOH (5 g; 0.012 mole) and finely powdered urea (0.75 g; 0.012 mole) was mixed and heated in slow stream of nitrogen. The temperature was gradually raised up to around 200° to bring the mixture into molten form. Subsequently, the temperature was retained between $130-140^\circ$. The nitrogen flow removed ammonia and water from the reaction site. The crude reaction product was then cooled and extracted with chloroform to give Cy_3SnNCO , which was recrystallized from petroleum ether/chloroform mixture; yield 50%; m.p. 100° . Analysis; Found: C, 55.58; H, 8.06; N, 3.38; Sn, 28.88. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{36}NOSn$; C, 55.63; H, 8.10; N, 3.41; Sn, 28.93%.

Cy_3SnNCS : It was prepared by metathetical reaction of equimolar ratio of silver thiocyanate and tricyclohexyltin iodide in refluxing chloroform for 2 hr. The precipitated silver iodide was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated and the compound was recrystallized from hexane to give crystals of Cy_3SnNCS ; m.p. $121-22^\circ$ (lit.¹⁵ 123°).

Cy_3SnNCS was also obtained by heating the tricyclohexyltin hydroxide and thiourea in a nitrogen atmosphere. Thus, equal molar mixture of Cy_3SnOH and thiourea was fused at $180-200^\circ$ and the temperature was then kept between $130-140^\circ$ for 4 hr in a slow stream of nitrogen. The intermediate products, ammonia and water, were removed by nitrogen and the crude product was refluxed with chloroform and filtered off. The product was concentrated and kept in ice cold water

for 15 min. White needle like crystals formed were separated by filtration and characterized as $(Cy_3Sn)_2S$; yield about 50%. The filtrate on concentration gave 20% of Cy_3SnNCS , recrystallized with petroleum ether; m.p. 120° (lit.¹⁵ 123°) and $(Cy_3Sn)_2S$; m.p. $130-31^\circ$.

$(Cy_3Sn)_2S$ obtained in the above reaction was confirmed by mixed melting point of an authentic sample prepared as given below.

H_2S gas was passed in hot alcoholic solution of Cy_3SnOH , followed by cooling when needle shaped crystals were obtained almost quantitatively which were recrystallized from methanol; m.p. 134° . Analysis; Found: C, 56.22; H, 8.62; Sn, 30.82; S, 4.12. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{72}Sn_2S$; C, 56.27, H, 8.65; Sn, 30.89; S, 4.17%.

Results and Discussion

Apart from the common methods of metathetical reactions employed for obtaining the tricyclohexyltin derivatives, the isocyanate was also obtained by the fusion of a mixture containing equimolar ratios of Cy_3SnOH or the *bis*-oxide and urea at about 200° for 15 min and then at $130-140^\circ$ for 4 hr in 50% yield. A plausible mechanism for the formation of cyanate by fusion with urea is the formation of isocyanic acid (HNCO) at fusion temperature of urea (Eq. 1) followed by its action on the oxide or hydroxide (Eq. 2).

It is expected that at such temperatures the hydroxide would get dehydrated into the *bis*-oxide.

These reactions are substantiated by the facts that (i) both ammonia and water vapour could be detected escaping through the condenser top, and (ii) preformed isocyanic acid reacts independently with organotin and antimony oxides¹⁶.

Attempts to extend the reaction for obtaining Cy_3SnNCS by using thiourea in place of urea resulted in the formation of only a small percentage of Cy_3SnNCS along with considerable amount of $(Cy_3Sn)_2S$ (cf: experimental) together with escaping ammonia and water. Repeating the experiment in an inert hydrocarbon solvent having boiling point higher than water (e.g., toluene) resulted once again in the formation of the *bis*-sulphide along with some unidentified product. These observations are similar to those obtained by Cummins and Dunn⁷ for tributyltin compounds using the fusion method and Raymond *et al*¹⁸ using acetonitrile as solvent for the phenyltin compounds.

The fusion reaction of hydroxide and thiourea resulted in the formation of mostly the *bis*-sulfide and to some extent of the thiocyanate unlike the reaction reported by Raymond *et al*¹⁸ in acetonitrile who reported the formation of dicyanamide

and bis-triphenyltin carbodimide. The reaction of tricyclohexyltin compounds and thiourea in toluene or at fusion temperature resulted only in the bis-sulfide and the thiocyanate. Some unidentified products obtained in this work could be the cyanamide and carbodimide which could not be separated or identified conclusively. These reactions have been independently and adequately worked up by a number of investigators¹⁵⁻¹⁸ for other triorganotin moieties and are not discussed any further. The cyclohexyl group does not behave differently under these reaction conditions.

Infra-red spectra: All the four pseudohalide groups (viz. NCO, NCS, NCSe and NC) are capable of exhibiting linkage isomerism and have facinated several past workers of group IV organometallic chemistry¹⁹⁻²⁰. However, it appears that this is for the first time that an attempt has been made to investigate structurally these anions in combination with a tricyclohexyltin moiety. This is important in view of the anomalous behaviour observed earlier for tricyclohexyltin acetate.

Cy₃SnNCS: A very strong broad band of the asymmetric -NCS stretching with the centre at 2062 cm⁻¹ suggests the bonding to be iso(-NCS) i.e., the group is attached through the nitrogen end with the tin metal. Apart from the shape and intensity of the band which has been used to distinguish between the two isomers in the past²¹ other important factors in favour of nitrogen linkage are:

(1) The smaller size and greater electronegativity of N permits a stronger dπ and pπ bond between tin and nitrogen than with diffuse p orbitals of the S atom.

(2) R₃Sn⁺(IV) being a hard acid according to HSAB concept would prefer to attach itself to the hard base, that is N rather than S of the thiocyanate²².

(3) Unlike the organometallics of transition metals, no group(IV) thiocyanate is as yet known to have a S-bonded linkage.

Cy₃SnNCO: In general, oxygen bonded cyanate with metals are rare and the nitrogen bonded products are more common for main group metals. The strong asymmetric -NCO band 2222 cm⁻¹ is in the region of reported triorganotin isocyanates. A few inorganic cyanates reported have much lower values for the asymmetric stretch. The bonding -NCO was also observed as a very weak band at around 610 cm⁻¹^{19,20}.

Cy₃SnNC: The only characteristic band observed for the cyanide is the asymmetric -CN stretching at 2150 cm⁻¹ which is closer to organic isonitriles 2160-2120 cm⁻¹, rather than the nitriles 2260-2220 cm⁻¹. However, taking into consideration the heavy mass of the central atom tin and comparatively high m.p. and low solubility, a polymeric carbon bonded cyanide structure is most likely as has been reported earlier from this laboratory²³ for other triorganotin cyanides.

Cy₃SnSeCN: The SeCN group like the -SCN gives rise to three fundamental modes of vibration. The iso -NCSe and normal -SeCN forms can be distinguished by the C-Se stretching at 630 ± 20 cm⁻¹ for the iso and 530 ± 10 cm⁻¹ for the normal forms²⁴. The tricyclohexyltin (iso) selenocyanate show a broad band of 605 cm⁻¹ which suggests Sn-NCSe bonding. The theoretical reasons advanced earlier for the bonding in the thiocyanate derivatives are equally valid for the selenocyanate as well, and add further support to tin-nitrogen bonding in the molecule. Once again all the organometal selenocyanates, Tl²⁵, Te²⁶, Ge, Sn¹⁹ Pb²⁵, reported so far possess an - iso bonding.

Cy₃SnN₃: The azide group in tricyclohexyltin azide, though not capable of showing structural isomerism, provides enough evidences in favour of a covalently bonded group. This is evident from its high solubility in organic solvents, smooth and sharp melting point and the asymmetric stretching at 2065 cm⁻¹ followed by bands at 1280 cm⁻¹ and 670 cm⁻¹ which agree well with earlier reports regarding the covalent bonded triorganotin azides from this laboratory²⁷.

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION OF THE PSEUDOHALIDES. WAVE LENGTH IN cm⁻¹

Compound	asym	sym	δ
(C ₆ H ₁₁) ₃ SnNCO	2222 vs	1350 m	615 w
(C ₆ H ₁₁) ₃ SnNC	2150 vs	—	—
(C ₆ H ₁₁) ₃ SnNCS	2062 vs	1040 m	670 ± 5 m
(C ₆ H ₁₁) ₃ SnNCSe	2050 vs	605 m	480 m
(C ₆ H ₁₁) ₃ SnN ₃	2065 vs	1285 m	670 m

asym = asymmetric, sym = symmetric, vs = very strong, m = medium, w = weak.

The adsorption associated with the tricyclohexyltin moiety agree well with those reported earlier in combination with the anion (OH⁻ and CO₃²⁻)²⁸ and hence are not listed or discussed.

The preferred equilibrium solid state molecular structure for tin in most triorganotin compounds containing uninegative anions R₃SnX is polymeric trigonal bipyramid, where the three organic groups are arranged on the planar ring and the anion X acts as bridging group above and below the plane of the ring⁷. The angular distortions from perfect geometry are generally in the directions dictated by the isovalent hybridization or VSEPR theories. The role of steric bulk of the organic group or the anion is crucial in deciding the structure and no authentic hexacoordinated R₃Sn derivative is yet known. In the tricyclohexyltin compounds reported in this work, the ir bands, the high m.p. all above 100 with exception where X = Br (m.p. 77°) and I (m.p. 65°) are in favour of an associated trigonal bipyramidal structure. These physical data compare very favourably with the corresponding phenyl, methyl and butyl compounds, all of which have associated structures. Further support of the tricyclohexyltin compounds can only be had through single crystal analysis. The exception of bromine

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF TRICYCLOHEXYLTIN COMPOUNDS

Compound	Antibacterial activity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)*					Antifungal activity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)*					
	<i>S.a.</i>	<i>S.t.</i>	<i>E.c.</i>	<i>K.p.</i>	<i>S.f.</i>	<i>C.n.</i>	<i>T.m.</i>	<i>A.n.</i>	<i>A.f.</i>	<i>M.c.</i>	<i>C.a.</i>
Cy_3SnNCS	0.78	>100	>100	1.75	1.56	0.78	12.5	25.5	12.5	12.5	1.56
Cy_3SnNCO	0.78	>100	>100	1.75	1.56	0.78	12.5	25.5	12.5	12.5	1.56
Cy_3SnNC	0.78	>100	>100	1.75	1.56	0.78	25	25.5	12.5	25.5	1.56
$\text{Cy}_3\text{SnNCS}_2$	0.78	>100	>100	1.75	1.56	0.78	6.25	25.5	12.5	12.5	1.56
Cy_3SnN_2	3.25	>100	>100	1.75	12.5	0.78	12.5	25.5	12.5	12.5	1.56
Cy_3SnOH	1.56	>100	>100	3.12	6.25	1.56	6.25	1.56	6.25	3.25	6.25
Cy_3SnCl	3.25	>100	>100	6.25	12.5	3.125	6.25	0.78	6.25	3.125	12.5
Cy_3SnBr	3.25	>100	>100	3.12	12.5	3.125	6.25	0.78	12.5	3.125	12.5
Cy_3SnI	6.25	>100	>100	6.25	12.5	12.5	6.25	0.78	12.5	2.125	12.5
$\text{Cy}_3\text{SnOOCCH}_3$	3.25	>100	>100	3.12	6.25	1.56	1.56	3.25	12.5	1.56	6.25

Cy=CyClO-C₆H₁₁. *All these compounds were tested *in vitro* for antibacterial activity against *S.a.*=*S. aureus*, *S.t.*=*S. typhi*, *E.c.*=*E. coli*, *K.p.*=*K. pneumoniae*, *S.f.*=*S. faecalis*, and antifungal activity against *C.n.*=*neoformans*, *T.m.*=*T. mentagrophytes*, *A.n.*=*A. niger*, *A.f.*=*A. fumigatus*, *M.c.*=*M. canis*, *C.a.*=*C. albicans*. The minimum inhibitory concentration was expressed in terms of microgram per millilitre ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) at which the growth of test organism was completely inhibited.

and iodine may be due to both the bulkier and weak coordinating nature of these anions which may favour four coordination and a monomeric structure to these compounds. The steric effect of the pseudohalides of this investigation is considerably reduced when we consider that the N bonded isomers have a linear arrangement of the three atoms -N=C=X as compared to the bent chalcogen (O, S, Se) isomer²⁴. It may be added that the only examples of the completely characterized four coordinated triorganotin system, tricyclohexyltin acetate and trifluoro acetate⁶, have infrared frequencies very different from other polymeric triorganotin acetates. These molecules adopt a flattened tetrahedral structure with wide carbon angle at tin as expected from both electron redistribution in the frame work and steric repulsion of bulky cyclohexane ring. The quadrupole splittings of the fluoride and chloride are similar to those reported for the methyltin analogues indicating five coordinate structure. In contrast, the bromide and iodide give quadrupole splittings which are midway between those found for polymeric trimethyltin and monomeric trineophenyltin bromide and iodide indicating a very weak intermolecular association if at all²⁵.

In view of the above facts the bromide and the iodide offer a good example which requires single crystal X-ray analyses to confirm the above predictions.

Biological activity: The antimicrobial activity of tricyclohexyltin halides and pseudohalides was examined *in vitro* against six species of fungi, *C. albicans*, *C. neoformans*, *M. canis*, *A. niger*, *A. Fumigatus*, *T. mentagrophytes*, and five species of bacteria, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *E. Coil*, *S. faecalis*, *K. pneumoniae*. The compounds exhibited higher activity *in vitro*.

It has been reported that triorganotin R₃SnX compounds where R=*n*Bu, Cy-C₆H₁₁, Ph and neophenyl are widely used in industry as biocides. Their biological activity is due mostly to the

organotin part of the molecule²⁶. It can be seen that the high antimicrobial activity of tricyclohexyltin compounds compare favourably with that of phenyl tin compounds and some cases possess even higher activity.

The antimicrobial activity of ethanolic solution of the compounds has been ascertained by twofold serial dilution method-Sabourauds and nutrient broths were used as test media for fungi and bacteria respectively. The maximum concentration of the compounds tested was 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The bacteria used were *S. aureus*, resistant in 2500 units penicillin/ml. The fungi were incubated at 25 $\pm$ 1° and the bacteria at 37°; incubation period for both was 24 hr. The antibacterial and antifungal activities are listed in Table 2.

An excellent activity is observed against penicillin resistant gram-positive *S. aureus*, while the gram negative species *S. typhi* and *E. coli* appears better to extremely resistant, to all tricyclohexyltin halides. Organotin pseudohalide compounds were found most active against the fungi *C. neoformans*. Once again, better than the halide in particular, they have been shown to inhibit only gram positive bacteria. The large activity of tricyclohexyltin halides and pseudohalides may be attributed to the presence of cyclohexyl moiety and a pseudohalide group.

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